

**JPL OPEN SOURCED SCIENCE (OSS)
FOR NASA EARTH SYSTEM OBSERVATORY (ESO)
MISSION SCIENCE DATA PROCESSING STUDY**

Sources Sought/Request for Information (RFI)

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PART 1. COMPANY INFORMATION

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COMPANY DESCRIPTION AND PAST PERFORMANCE

KBR provides full life-cycle cloud infrastructure engineering, Agile/DevSecOps support, data science, and science data management services to NASA, USGS, NOAA, DoD, and multiple other agencies. Our cloud infrastructure engineering experience includes designing, maintaining, and optimizing cloud architectures using Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft Azure, and Google Cloud Platform, tailored to meet the diverse needs of our clients. We use Agile, DevSecOps, and user-centered design principles and practices to support modernization, application development, and sustainment services, focusing on security, reliability, and sustainability.

KBR has a long history with the NASA’s EOSDIS Program and related programs for other agencies, including USGS and NOAA. In support of the USGS EROS Center, KBR has been the prime contractor supporting the Land Processing DAAC for more than a decade. As part of this effort, we have not only performed operations and maintenance of the on-premise infrastructure, but also developed new tools to support scientific research, such as the Application for Extracting and Exploring Analysis Ready Samples (AppEEARS). At the LP DAAC, KBR worked with NASA to develop the Operational Recovery Cloud Archive (ORCA), part of ESDIS’ 3-2-1 data preservation strategy, providing a cloud-based operational backup to support science data recovery. KBR has also supported EOSDIS as a subcontractor to Raytheon under EED2 and EED3, supporting NGAP, sustainment of the CMR, and Agile development. In addition, KBR was the prime contractor for development of the ICESat data processing system, which provides ICESat data products to the National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC). As a subcontractor on the SESDA contract, KBR supports the Goddard Earth Sciences Data and Information Services Center (GES DISC). KBR is the prime contractor for NASA’s Ground Systems and Mission Operations (GSMO) contract, providing flight operations for NASA Earth-observing satellites.

For the USGS, KBR operates, maintains, and sustains the USGS National Satellite Land Remote Sensing Data Archive (NSLRSDA), which includes both unprocessed satellite data and higher level data products that support environmental research, policy analysis, and decision-making across US agencies. Over the past 5 years, KBR has significantly advanced data management capabilities for the Landsat Program, including the development of gridded, Analysis Ready Data (ARD) products; Land Change Monitoring, Assessment and Projection (LCMAP) time series data products; and a variety of specialized products, such as those supporting the Landscape Fire and Resource Management Planning Tools (LANDFIRE) Program, using Google Earth Engine as well as on-premise infrastructure. KBR performed a comprehensive migration of Landsat data processing to USGS’ AWS environment to support more efficient processing, additional capacity, and better availability to users.

For NOAA, KBR provides support to the National Centers for Environment Information (NCEI), which is a consumer of EOSDIS products and other environmental data products in support of NOAA scientific research and data product development.

PART 2: RESPONSES TO TOPIC AREAS (1), (2), (3), AND (5)

1. Data Processing System Architecture: Cloud 3.0—An Interplanetary Operating System

Problem Statement

Cloud resource and infrastructure providers are silos. While data has gravity, cloud-vendor competition produces a healthy ecosystem of alternative solutions that may attract different users. ESO needs to enable globally distributed computing and distribution systems for scientific data using a combination of cloud infrastructure, on-premises systems, and ephemeral resources.

Solution Description

An Interplanetary Operating System (IP-OS) is a way to harness traditional cloud-provider solutions, on-premises systems, and ephemeral resources in a way that mitigates the cause and effect of data gravity. Its fundamental capabilities support reproducible data processing, high-performance global distribution of data, and facilities to encourage participation and build trust between participants. ESO should define a Cloud 3.0 strategy and establish agreements among infrastructure providers, data science practitioners, and system integrators in order to adopt or build a reference implementation of an IP-OS, to include a technical architecture, standards and technologies, and an initial prototype.

Enabling Technologies

1. **Interplanetary File System**— A peer-to-peer, globally distributed, content addressable data distribution and retrieval system, commonly referred to as the content-addressable web.
2. **Interplanetary Linked Data**—IPLD is the data model of the content-addressable web. It treats all hash-linked data structures as subsets of a unified information space, unifying all data models that link data with hashes as instances of IPLD. It enables provenance, discoverability, and exploration-related use cases.
3. **Distributed Ledger**—An immutable append-only log supporting use cases related to publication of data and models, requests and offers for processing and storage, as well as assertions about validity and verification of data and models. This is an essential component that enables reproducibility of data.
4. **WebAssembly (WASM) Models**—An executable format specifically designed for secure execution of untrusted code. WASM is a compilation target for a growing number of programming languages. It enables use cases related to the execution of models or other IP-OS related code in a globally distributed environment.
5. **Containerized Models**— An alternative executable format using Open Container Initiative (OCI) or Docker format images for publishing and executing models that cannot be compiled to WASM.

Use cases include typical transactions (e.g., publishing and retrieving data collections, executable models, derivative collections, subsets, tools, applications, source code, metadata regarding provenance and quality), as implemented across cloud and infrastructure providers.

2. Open Science: Algorithm Accessibility and Reproducibility

Problem Statement

Acceptance of science algorithms that process, analyze, fuse, and generate Earth Science data hinges both on reproducibility of results and on establishing value, potentially by applying an algorithm from one study area to other areas, or by applying single granule analysis across an entire data collection. While reproducibility is currently supported by metadata indicating provenance, additional tooling can provide a consistent publication approach for algorithm developers and cloud providers.

Solution Descriptions

ESO can specifically support reproducibility by adopting a common methodology to bring algorithms and applications to the large sets of Earth Science data stored in the cloud, no matter the cloud provider storing them. With the evolution of code bundling, packaging, and build systems (many supported natively in the cloud), it will be possible to build a system that accepts as input a scientist's algorithm, plus data and metadata used to validate the algorithm's correct execution.

A diagram of a potential system is shown below.

A scientist would send an algorithm to the cloud as a bundle containing the algorithm plus input and output data to validate it in the cloud environment. The cloud processing system would package the code for deployment to compute resources specific to the particular cloud vendor and to consume and distribute data to the vendor's particular data storage systems in use for the dataset.

Upon the completion of the processing, the scientist could publish the algorithm and datasets for verification and use by the wider science community. This would enable other scientists to initially reproduce the original results, and then go through various validation steps (e.g., use of the algorithm on broader datasets, comparison to actual in-situ measurements).

An area for further work is the necessary feedback mechanisms (tools and governance) to allow scientists to document validity, their own results, and to note potential quality or correctness issues.

3. Component Technologies: Use of AI/ML Techniques to Optimize Research

Problem Statement

Breakthrough science will come through application of new techniques, such as Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML), in highly scalable environments such as cloud computing. We recommend infusing AI/ML techniques and expertise to address existing data quality, data discovery, access, and use challenges.

Solution Descriptions

- 1. Synthetic data** is data that is artificially or programmatically generated, as opposed to ‘real’ data that is collected through real-world surveys or events. A good synthetic dataset can capture the underlying structure and display the same statistical distributions as the original data, rendering it indistinguishable from the real one. Common issues when developing machine learning models include missing data and skewed distribution of data classes. For example, when classifying vegetation type, certain vegetation types have more data than others and this can result in unintended biases in models. Using AI to generate synthetic data can reduce model biases associated with non-uniform data sets. We recommend providing AI models for creation and management of synthetic data. These data can be used either alone or in conjunction with real data to validate mathematical models and to train machine learning models.
- 2. AI/ML Metadata Repository.** To increase reusability of existing work with AI/ML models, and to support discovery of models, we recommend enhancing the current CMR to include AI/ML model attributes. Attributes would include Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for training data set(s), ML algorithm used, a DOI validation data set, number of input features, number of derived features, output features, hyper parameter values, etc. Additional metadata parameters will be based on the ML algorithm used. We recommend developing a tool like NASA's Inter-agency Implementation and Advanced Concepts Team (IMPACT) Algorithm Publication Tool (APT) that enables open, reproducible science by helping scientists write standardized, high-quality algorithm documentation collaboratively. We recommend an enhancing APT tool to support AI/ML tools. We recommend creating a ‘hub’ for AI/ML models and tools.
- 3. Supporting Data Fusion and ML Across Clouds.** We recommend that ESO adopt tools like Google’s BigQuery Omni, to facilitate analysis of data stored in multiple public clouds. Data fusion integrates multiple data sources to produce broader, more consistent, and more useful information. It is a very likely scenario that scientists using AI/ML algorithms would be combining multiple data sources. The cost of moving data between cloud providers is not sustainable for many agencies, and it’s still difficult to seamlessly work across clouds. BigQuery Omni represents a new way of analyzing data stored in multiple public clouds by decoupling compute and storage. By decoupling these two, BigQuery provides scalable storage that can reside in Google Cloud or other public clouds, and stateless resilient compute that executes standard SQL queries. We would also recommend the use of a multi-cloud data lake architecture for fused data storage with tools such as Google’s BigQuery Omni to analyze data across clouds, BigQuery to bring compute to stored data, and Big Query ML to reduce the learning curve associated with using ML, all within a multi-cloud environment.

5. Other Recommendations

AI Ethics and AI Governance

As AI/ML-based systems become the algorithms of choice to enable breakthrough science, we recommend setting up an AI Ethics and AI Governance structure that helps develop trust in ML models being developed in the Open Science Environment. From an ethical perspective, AI should be fair and inclusive in its assertions, be accountable for its decisions, be socially beneficial, and offer explainability and transparency. The three cornerstones of AI governance are trust, transparency, and diversity. Technologies such as distributed ledger can be employed to govern trust, transparency, and diversity, thereby providing immutability across multi-cloud providers.

- For trust, we recommend defining trust levels for data in order to distinguish fully trusted data from least trusted data. Formulate guidelines for the training and modification of models, so published models can be trusted.
- For transparency, we recommend extending existing data lineage and metadata guidelines for data derivatives. Develop mechanisms to identify when black-box approaches to models are suitable and should make the trade-off between accuracy and explainability on a case-by-case basis.
- For diversity, we recommend improving data diversity to counter incomplete or biased information in data. Governance and metadata should support mechanisms to consciously seek diverse outcomes by employing various algorithms, giving the intended audience the option to select what it considers to be the best answer in the context.

Optimize Research and Data Discovery

There are limitations to how many articles a PI, scientist, researcher, and decision maker can reasonably be expected to read in a year. By utilizing AI Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, research can easily get a list of relevant and similar publications to their area of research. By using NLP, users can search across DOI objects that include documents, algorithms, etc.

Tools and Training

ESO should work with organizations such as Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP) to provide tools and training to scientists to be better able to collaborate with all types of computational and computer scientists. We recommend using data science working/advisory groups to bring together researchers and computer scientists to discuss and share advances in AI/ML for use in open science, current events, best practices, and to share use cases where AI/ML was successfully used.